

On the feasibility of RAN scaling for beyond 5G networks: Proactive CU-UP Scaling with ML Demand Forecasting

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Abstract—Fifth generation (5G) and beyond cellular networks bring significant advantages over their predecessors in the RAN part of the network, as they are based on a disaggregated, cloud-based architecture, marking a major shift from the monolithic designs of previous generations. This disaggregated approach has led to the development of Virtual RAN (V-RAN) and Open RAN (O-RAN) architectures, which provide greater flexibility in deployment while optimizing costs and resource utilization. Simultaneously, the increasing demands for high-speed, low-latency connectivity to support diverse 5G applications such as IoT, V2X, and URLLC highlight the critical need for reliable and scalable network solutions. In this paper, we address the scalability challenges of the CU-UP component, identified as a bottleneck in the 5G disaggregated RAN, particularly under high traffic loads. We propose a proactive horizontal scaling mechanism for the CU-UP, leveraging machine learning to forecast traffic demands. This involves using an xApp on the Near-RT RIC that integrates a pre-trained Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model using a real-world dataset which predicts traffic demands, enabling proactive scaling of CU-UP instances ahead of peak periods to maintain Quality of Service (QoS). The proposed mechanism was implemented and evaluated using real-world testbeds under dynamic conditions, demonstrating its effectiveness in practical environments. Our findings emphasize the importance of integrating ML techniques to forecast network loads accurately and adapting such scaling mechanisms in 5G systems to reduce packet loss and unnecessary scaling overhead while ensuring smoother operation during high-demand periods.

Index Terms—5G O-RAN, 5G-RAN scaling, CU-UP scaling, traffic forecasting, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

5G is the latest and most advanced generation of cellular networks and is addressing a high increase in subscribers and connected devices resulting in increased demands and traffic loads over the network. To meet high-volume data transmission and low-latency demands of services, 5G and beyond networks adopt a disaggregated component architecture in both the 5G Core Network (5GCN) and the Radio Access Network (RAN), utilizing a Network Function Virtualization (NFV) based architecture. NFV decouples network functions

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from dedicated hardware devices, enabling them to run as virtualized instances on computing platforms, offering flexibility and scalability for the 5GCN and 5G RAN deployment. The adoption of a disaggregated architecture in the RAN led to the transformation from the monolithic deployment of gNB to its cloud-based version (namely C-RAN) and further evolved into a virtualized architecture (V-RAN), with the creation of separate entities responsible for managing specific parts of the 5G NR protocol stack, resulting in various versions of the RAN functional split [1]. The split standardized for 5G networks is the 3GPP Option 2, according to which the C-RAN architecture comprises the Central Unit (CU), which hosts the network layer functionalities (PDPC, RRC/SDAP), and the Distributed Unit (DU), which is responsible for the Data Link Layer and handles the physical layer and over-the-air transmission (PHY, MAC, RLC).

5G also supports the separation of the control plane (CP) and the user plane (UP) allowing independent management of signaling and data traffic, and significantly improving network flexibility and scalability. Following this plane separation, the CU can be further divided into the CU-CP, responsible for signaling (PDCP and RRC), and the CU-UP, responsible for the data path (PDCP and SDAP), thereby separating its procedural functionalities. The CU-UP handles critical tasks such as Service Data Adaptation Protocol (SDAP) marking, Packet Data Convergence Protocol (PDCP) ciphering, packet switching/routing, and header compression. Furthermore, CU-UP is responsible for managing traffic from multiple Distributed Units (DUs), leading to processing high packet volumes, which impact its reliability under heavy traffic and are identified as a potential data bottleneck in the RAN [2].

The O-RAN architecture complements the C-RAN version of 5G, with the aim of enhancing the flexibility and efficiency of 5G deployments. The goal of O-RAN is to introduce open interfaces and standards in order to provide interoperability among multi-vendor equipment. One of the most important features of O-RAN is also the introduction of a Near-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC) into 5G RAN networks, used to improve the functionality of 5G RAN through monitoring and analysis of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as throughput, latency, and resource

utilization. The existence of KPIs enables the Near-RT RIC to perform intelligent traffic management and make operational decisions, which dynamically manage RAN functionalities such as traffic optimization and resource allocation, enhancing network adaptability. Additionally, the existence of a Non-Real-Time RAN Intelligent Controller (Non-RT RIC) is introduced that supports non-real-time radio resource management, higher-layer procedure optimization, policy optimization in the RAN, and provides AI/ML models to support the operation of near-Real Time RIC.

In this work, we deploy a fully disaggregated 5G O-RAN network that supports the separation of the Control Plane (CP) and User Plane (UP) with the existence of a near-RT RIC, alongside a service-based 5G Core Network (CN), in a fully cloud-based deployment utilizing the state-of-the-art Kubernetes (k8s) service orchestrator. We developed an ML model based on Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) using a real-world dataset to forecast the future load demands of UEs and designed and implemented a proactive CU-UP scaling mechanism based on these predictions. Incorporating machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) approaches can significantly improve the flexibility of 5G systems [3]. By adopting these techniques in 5G networks, future network states, such as User Equipment (UE) mobility and load requirements, can be predicted, and thus decisions can be made proactively to transform and adapt networks to meet the future needs of their subscribers. This approach not only ensures more efficient resource utilization but also improves the user experience and maintains high Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE) by addressing network congestion proactively. Unlike approaches limited to simulation environments, we evaluate our proposed mechanism under real-world traffic conditions and environment, demonstrating its practical applicability using a testbed infrastructure.

The main contributions of this work can be summarized to:

- Design and implement an xApp for dynamic horizontal CU-UP scaling-in a 5G O-RAN system, leveraging forecasting of UE traffic load.
- Validate the proposed xApp and scaling mechanism using real-world traffic in a testbed environment.
- Compare reactive and proactive CU-UP scaling mechanisms, highlighting the advantages of proactive scaling.
- Provide a proof-of-concept on the horizontal scaling mechanism for the RAN.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II provides an overview of the related literature, focusing on scaling approaches used in VNFs generally, followed by a detailed examination of scaling-in the 5GCN and RAN. Section III provides our system model architecture and configuration, and Section IV evaluates our implementation presenting our experiment setup and the experiment results. Finally, in Section VI we conclude and discuss future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

In order to introduce a proactive scaling mechanism to a 5G O-RAN system, it is essential to first examine the methods and

strategies used for scaling especially in cloud-based network systems. In this context, VNF scaling has played a major role, since it enables dynamic resource allocation by adjusting the capacity of virtual network functions to meet fluctuating network demands. Authors in [4] and [5] perform proactive VNF scaling based on the forecast client demands using online learning and optimization techniques. Their methods result to the minimization of costs and overall improved service quality in dynamic simulated NFV environments. In [6], the authors describe a VNF scaling process based on forecast UE demands comparing three ML models ARIMA, XGBoost, and LSTM, using a real-world dataset to emulate network load from 4G base stations, without applying this mechanism to a specific 5G NF.

Noticeable work has been done on the scaling of the Access and Mobility Function (AMF) in the 5GCN. Authors in [7] introduce a CNN-LSTM model to predict traffic loads for proactive scaling of the AMF component. They evaluate the proposed methods using real-world data in a simulated environment, enabling efficient and proactive resource management, focusing on prediction accuracy and minimizing training duration. In [8], the authors implement a dynamic horizontal scaling mechanism for the AMF while considering factors such as the number of connected UEs, the number of active AMFs and resource allocation information. Using a real-world dataset, the authors train a WaveNet Deep Neural Network (DNN) to classify system states based on demand and decide on scaling horizontally the AMF.

The UPF scaling has been also discussed in the scientific community based on the potential benefits it can bring since it is the only component in the 5GCN user plane. In [9], the authors present a mechanism for the dynamic management of 5GCN functions, focusing on UPF scaling based on real-time monitoring of node CPU usage. This work aims to prevent network congestion, enhance network performance, and provide valuable techniques for managing the resource allocation. In [10], authors propose an auto-scaling UPF system using real-time traffic demands monitoring named Bit rate Aware Auto Scaling (BAAS), relying on simulations, with the reference architecture based on LTE rather than a native 5G framework. Authors in [11] investigate vertical, horizontal and hybrid scaling strategies for VNFs of a 5G Network such as the UPF and application VNFs hosted on MEC servers. Their findings highlight that vertical scaling optimizes resource usage, while horizontal scaling improves the scalability and reliability of the system. To balance these benefits, a heuristic algorithm is developed, which implements a hybrid strategy that dynamically selects between vertical and horizontal scaling based on the requirements of each scenario. In [12] a real-time scaling mechanism for VPP-based UPFs is proposed. The work is using the VPP rate, which reflects the number of packets processed at once, as a key indicator. This mechanism relies on a system that monitors and analyzes traffic to adjust the number of UPFs as needed. Work [13] presents an AI-driven system that dynamically scales the

Fig. 1: Proactive scaling O-RAN system architecture

UPF component using a Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) framework based on real-time traffic demands, ensuring QoS while minimizing CPU and power usage.

Scaling the 5G-RAN VNFs is a topic that has not been extensively explored. Specifically focusing on the RAN, an interesting study by Mudvari et al. [14] presents an ML-driven dynamic scaling approach for the user plane components of 5G. The authors utilize four ML models to forecast network load using a real-world dataset and dynamically implement a proactive scaling mechanism that adjusts either the resources of the monolithic gNB (vertical scaling) or the instances of the UPF (horizontal scaling). A notable study [15] focuses on RAN components and implements a methodology to illustrate the scaling requirements for the CU, DU, and Near-RT RIC. The authors use an ILP model driven by forecast demands generated by two ML models, LSTM and ARIMA. The ILP model determines the optimal number of instances needed for the scaled components. However, their work is limited to traffic prediction and theoretical scaling strategies, as they do not implement or evaluate the scaling mechanism in practice.

Our work differentiates from the existing literature since it expands the research in scaling the 5G infrastructure, moving beyond scaling-in the 5GCN to focus on the scaling of actual user plane RAN components. Contrary to existing works, we progress beyond existing state-of-the-art and explore the benefits of horizontal scaling at the RAN part. Existing works that have explored RAN scaling, focus on the vertical scaling process (i.e. adding more computational resources to the function), contrary to our approach (spawning multiple replicas of the RAN function and direct traffic to them). By leveraging real-world testbeds, our work demonstrates the practical applicability of a proactive scaling mechanism for the CU-UP component driven by forecast traffic demands of the clients in an O-RAN environment.

III. SYSTEM MODEL AND ARCHITECTURE

This section provides an extensive analysis of all the components of a 5G network that supports proactive CU-UP scaling based on predicted UE traffic demands, detailing both

the design of our proposed system architecture as depicted in Figure 1 and the experimental setup as shown in Figure 2.

A. 5G Network Configuration and Setup

The proposed 5G system deploys both the 5GCN and the RAN in a cloud-based environment to enable virtualization, utilizing Kubernetes, an open-source container orchestration platform, as the orchestration tool for these components. For our system architecture and experiment definition, we employ the popular OpenAirInterface (OAI) platform, which offers a software-based implementation of the 5GCN, RAN and RIC. For the 5GCN deployment, we deploy a basic network, which includes the Authentication Server Function (AUSF), the Unified Data Management (UDM), the User Data Repository (UDR), the Network Repository Function (NRF), the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), the Session Management Function (SMF), and a simple User Plane Function (UPF) component. In our experimental setup, we deploy two UPFs; as prior works have shown (e.g. [16]) the selection of the UPF can highly affect the overall throughput that the 5G network can achieve. As we are using the softwarized UPF provided by OAI, that is reported to achieve less throughput than other hardware based alternatives, we opt to deploy two UPFs in order to increase the overall network capacity of the 5G network. By following such an approach in our setup, and using the disaggregated RAN deployment options, the CU-UP is now the only congestion point in the datapaths of the UEs under test.

Regarding the disaggregated RAN deployment, the system architecture is based on the 5G V-RAN network stack [17], in which the F1 interface is implemented as standardized in TS 38.470 - 38.473 [18] for 5G NR. More specifically, the F1 interface implements the 3GPP Option 2 split [19] which defines the functional split between the Centralized Unit (CU), integrating the PDCP, RRC, and SDAP layers, and the Distributed Unit (DU), which handles the RLC, MAC, and PHY layers. Additionally, we support the separation of the CU into two logical components: the CU Control Plane (CU-CP) and the CU User Plane (CU-UP) via the

E1 interface as defined in 3GPP TS 38.463 [20]. The CU-CP manages signaling and control-plane functionalities such as mobility management, bearer setup, and session handling, while the CU-UP is responsible for all the user-plane traffic (data traffic from the network). Putting everything together, the components of our experimental 5G RAN network are the following: CU-CP, CU-UP that can be scaled by our algorithm, 2 DUs, and 2 UEs. Similar to the approach that we follow for the 5GCN, we opt to use multiple DUs in order to have a higher overall network capacity, and have as a single point of stress for the data-plane traffic the CU-UP. The radio link between each UE and DU is not established over the air. Instead, we utilized the RF simulator, which emulates the functionality of an actual Radio Frequency (RF) board. We opt to simulate real-world channel conditions using a model with Additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). Given that the disaggregated 5G-RAN can also support further splitting of the DU to O-DU and O-RU, with the O-RU using real HW radios, our selection to emulate the radio part plays no significant role in the under-test system (the CU-UP) and only contributes to relieving any potential bottlenecks and truly stress-testing the system.

Since we base our system on the O-RAN architecture, all the RAN VNFs (CU-CP, CU-UPs and DUs) deployed in this 5G-RAN are E2 nodes managed by the Near Real-Time Radio Intelligent Controller (Near-RT RIC). The communication between the RAN VNFs and the Near-RT RIC takes place over the E2 interface as specified in 3GPP TS 28.552 [21]. The Near-RT RIC plays an important role in managing and optimizing the various functions of the RAN components, through the continuous fetching of Key Performance Indicator metrics (KPIs) and Key Performance Measurements (KPMs) from the E2 nodes. In this work, we use the KPI *DRB.UEThpDl*. The metric is defined in the 3GPP TS 28.552 standard [21] and is measuring the DL bitrate per UE arriving at the CU-UP. For our system, and since the RAN part is based on OAI, we use FlexRIC as our controller [22]. The resulting system architecture used in our experiments is shown in Figure 2. Building on this foundation, we developed an xApp that continuously monitors the selected KPI from the CU-UP instance, and periodically (for our experiments the period is set to 5 seconds) it forecasts the next 10 values using a window of the most recent 40 values. The predictions are based on a pre-trained LSTM model, that is integrated to the xApp. This LSTM model was pretrained in the Non-RT RIC, according to Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework using the dataset described in IV-A and resulting the ML model in III-C. Based on the predicted values, the xApp decides according to predefined thresholds on whether the CU-UP instances of the 5G-VRAN should be scaled-out, scaled-in, or remain unchanged. It is important to mention that the proactive mechanism is operating exclusively in the scaling-out scenario (spawning multiple replicas) as performing proactive scaling-in (reducing the number of replicas) could result in packet loss due to the

system functioning with reduced resources. In Section IV-B, we also present experiments on a system that supports reactive scaling of the CU-UP instances. The key difference in the reactive implementation is that it does not forecast events; instead, the system continuously monitors client demands and triggers scaling only when real-time values exceed the predefined limits.

Fig. 2: Experimental 5G CN and O-RAN architecture

B. CU-UP Scaling Process

Horizontal scaling of network-based VNFs in real-world networks is not a straightforward procedure as it is in the cloud computing field. The scaled CU-UP instances is not just about replicating the same functionality but instead creating new instances of the CU-UP components, even with different IDs, which need to be properly integrated and synchronized with the rest of the network components, thus requiring updates to their configurations. This is why traditional k8s tools for horizontal scaling, such as the Horizontal Pod Autoscaler, are unsuitable for scaling real-world 5G components, as they simply replicate the same service without making any configuration changes. As several of these services are stateful, and require the synchronization of the different components, special handling needs to be in place in order to inform all the involved components of the new replicas.

To scale the CU-UP in a seamless and efficient manner, the system must support the CU-UP Change functionality, allowing each UE to switch its assigned CU-UP without deregistering from the network. Although the CU-UP Change procedure is specified in 3GPP Release 15 [19], OAI has not yet released a version that implements this functionality. In order to deal with this limitation, we implement a scaling mechanism that ensures no fault generation to the 5G network during the scale-out events by first deploying the additional CU-UP instance and then restarting the corresponding UE instances that will be assigned to it. For scale-in scenarios,

TABLE I: Node Assignments and Specifications

Node	Components	CPU	Cores	RAM
1	NRF, UDR, UDM, AUSF, AMF, SMF, CU-CP, FlexRIC	Intel Core Processor (Skylake, IBRS)	4	8GB
2,3	UPF (Slice: oai & ims)	Intel Core Processor (Skylake, IBRS)	4	8GB
4,5	CU-UPs	Intel Core Processor (Skylake, IBRS)	4	8GB
6	DU, UE (Pair 1)	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz	6	16GB
7	DU, UE (Pair 2)	Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8700 CPU @ 3.20GHz	6	16GB

firstly, we uninstall the surplus CU-UP instances, and immediately, we restart the UEs connected to the uninstalled CU-UP instances to trigger the reconnection with the 5G network and be assigned to the new ones. A limitation of this approach is the temporary interruption of the UE connections, which is caused by container restart, and packet loss which may occur during transmission when the UE is disconnected. The CU-UP Change procedure, as outlined in [19], facilitates data forwarding from the source gNB-CU-UP to the target gNB-CU-UP, thereby preventing packet loss during the CU-UP switch. To eliminate packet loss in our implementation, we monitor the UE connection state and ensure traffic generation to/from the UE only when it is connected to the network. In production systems, these network readjustments and manual checks could be bypassed by adopting the CU-UP Change mechanism with data forwarding fully enabled. In our implementation deploying new CU-UP instances requires negligible time, resulting in minimal impact on overall system performance.

C. Machine Learning Model - Demand Prediction

To forecast the future throughput values of the UEs, we replay a dataset as described in IV-A over the network, to generate traffic over the 5G network components. We collect the respective KPI values that are reported by the xApp, and try to predict the future demand over the network. We treat the specific problem as a time-series forecasting problem and choose to use the LSTM model, a popular DL model for forecasting the demand values of the UEs in 4G and 5G networks as illustrated in several works in relevant literature (e.g. [23], [24]). The model consists of three layers: two LSTM layers with 96 and 128 neurons respectively, followed by a dense output layer, which is able to predict the next 10 time steps based on an input sequence of 40 time steps. The model architecture resulted from using the keras-tuner, which gave us the optimal settings based on the training dataset and the numbers of the future time points that we wanted it to predict. The model was trained for 15 epochs using the Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0015, balancing sufficient training value and preventing overfitting, achieving accuracy of 5.6% MAPE. The primary purpose of this work is to study a 5G system that will be able to adapt the number of CU-UP instances based on the predicted throughput requirements of the UEs rather than optimizing the prediction model itself. For this reason, we did not compare the performance of the resulting LSTM with other ML models. The trained LSTM model was saved and integrated as a pre-trained model in our

Algorithm 1 Proactive CU-UP Scaling xApp

Require: Window Size W , Forecast Interval T , Prediction Horizon P
Require: Upper Threshold, Lower Threshold, Pretrained LSTM Model

- 1: **Initialize:** Sliding window $S[UE]$ with W historical DL throughput values per UE
- 2: **Initialize:** Real-time throughput $R[UE] \leftarrow 0$ for all UEs
- 3: **Initialize:** Load pretrained LSTM model
- 4: **Initialize:** Connect to RT-RIC and subscribe to the E2SM-KPM
- 5: **while true do**
- 6: **for** each CU-UP (Parallel) **do**
- 7: Fetch current DL throughput $R[UE]$ for each UE
- 8: Update $S[UE]$ by appending $R[UE]$ and remove oldest entry
- 9: **end for**
- 10: **if** Every T seconds **then**
- 11: **Forecasting:**
- 12: Initialize $\text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{total}} \leftarrow 0$
- 13: **for all** CU-UP (Parallel) **do**
- 14: **for all** UE served by CU-UP (Parallel) **do**
- 15: Predict the next P timesteps for each UE:
- 16: $\text{Thr_Pr}[UE] \leftarrow \text{LSTM}(S[UE])$
- 17: Compute $\text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{max}}[UE] \leftarrow \max(\text{Thr_Pr}[UE])$
- 18: Update $\text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{total}} \leftarrow \text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{total}} + \text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{max}}[UE]$
- 19: **end for**
- 20: **if** $\text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{total}} \geq \text{Upper Threshold}$ **then**
- 21: Append CU-UP to Scale_OUT_list
- 22: **end if**
- 23: **if** $\text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{total}} < \text{Lower Threshold}$ **then**
- 24: Append CU-UP to Scale_IN_list
- 25: **end if**
- 26: **end for**
- 27: **end if**
- 28: **Scaling Actions:**
- 29: **Scale-Out:**
- 30: **for all** CU-UP in Scale_OUT_list (Parallel) **do**
- 31: Deploy a new CU-UP
- 32: Distribute UEs evenly across the existing CU-UP and the new CU-UP
- 33: **end for**
- 34: **Scale-In:**
- 35: Create Pairs of CU-UP from the Scale_IN_list
- 36: **for all** Pairs of CU-UPs in Scale_IN_list (Parallel) **do**
- 37: Compute $\text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{total}}$ for the pair (CU_UP_i, CU_UP_j)
- 38: **if** $\text{Thr_Pr}_{\text{total}} < \text{Lower Threshold}$ **then**
- 39: **for** P timesteps **do**
- 40: Initialize $R_{\text{total}} \leftarrow 0$
- 41: **for all** UE served by the CU-UP pair (Parallel) **do**
- 42: Fetch current throughput $R[UE]$
- 43: Update sliding window $S[UE]$ with $R[UE]$ and remove the oldest entry
- 44: Update $R_{\text{total}} \leftarrow R_{\text{total}} + R[UE]$
- 45: **end for**
- 46: **if** $R_{\text{total}} < \text{Lower Threshold}$ **then**
- 47: Deallocate one CU-UP $(CU_UP_i \text{ or } CU_UP_j)$
- 48: Assign the UEs from CU_UP_i and CU_UP_j to the remaining CU-UP
- 49: **break**
- 50: **end if**
- 51: **end for**
- 52: **end if**
- 53: **end for**
- 54: **end if**
- 55: **end for**
- 56: **end for**
- 57: **end while**

xApp in order to predict the next 10 time steps in real-time, with the knowledge of the 40 previous values.

D. xApp Functionality

The proactive CU-UP scaling algorithm is designed to efficiently manage traffic loads in 5G O-RAN by forecasting future throughput demands and dynamically adjusting the number of CU-UP instances. This algorithm is implemented as part of an xApp deployed on the Near-RT RIC. Initially, the xApp retrieves a pre-trained machine learning model from the O-RAN Service Management and Orchestration (SMO) framework, connects to the Near-RT RIC, and subscribes to the Radio Config (RC) Key Performance Metrics (KPM) offered by the E2 Agent. These entities exist in the FlexRIC implementation that we are using for this work. In this work, only the CU-UP nodes of the RAN are enabled as E2 nodes, since the target is to exclusively retrieve KPIs from the CU-UP components. xApp retrieves the KPI *DRB.UETHpDI* from the E2 nodes every second and, at predefined intervals T (5 seconds in this case), it uses the pre-trained LSTM model to forecast the next predefined interval (10 seconds in this case) for each UE based on the previous W timesteps stored in a sliding window S . Then, it computes the total predicted throughput demand (Th_Pr_total) as the sum of the maximum predicted throughput values across all UEs per CU-UP. For each CU-UP that the computed total exceeds or equals a predefined upper threshold, the system scales-out by deploying a new CU-UP instance and redistributing the UEs evenly across the existing and newly deployed CU-UP. Contrary to this, if the total forecast throughput demand of the CU-UPs falls below a predefined lower threshold, the xApp initiates a scale-in procedure. During this process, it waits for the first value below the bottom threshold and subsequently destroys the excess CU-UPs and redistributes the UEs to the remaining active CU-UPs. The functionality of the xApp is summarized in Algorithm 1.

E. Experimentation environment

To deploy our system in a real-world experimental environment, we utilized the NITOS testbed, the Greek Node of the SLICES-RI [25], hosted at the University of Thessaly, Greece. NITOS is an open-access platform offering a controlled and robust environment for deploying 5G networks, showcasing the practical applicability of our system in real-world scenarios. Complemented with the SLICES-RI tools, the platform can easily deploy such cloud-native 5G networks as the one described in our architecture.

During the design phase, we determined the number of nodes required for component deployment and defined their assignments to ensure an optimal configuration. The components were allocated as follows: a single node was designated for all 5G control plane entities, including NRF, UDR, UDM, AUSF, AMF, SMF, and CU-CP. These components, while latency-sensitive, have minimal computational demands. Two additional nodes were reserved for potential CU-UP deployments. Furthermore, two nodes with similar latency to the CU-

UP nodes (approximately 0.7 ms) were selected for deploying the two UPFs. Lastly, two more nodes were allocated for the deployment of the two DU and UE pairs, which require significant computational resources and share a latency of approximately 0.5 ms with the CU-UP nodes. Table I provides a detailed overview of these assignments.

IV. EVALUATION

In this section we present our experimental findings. Initially, we present the dataset that we use to generate the respective traffic over the network, and subsequently the results and benefits that our solution provides.

A. Dataset

The public available dataset in [26] provides a 5G trace gathered from a major Irish mobile operator and offers two mobility patterns (car and static) and two application patterns (file download and video streaming). Out of the candidate mobility and application patterns we use the static one with a downloading application as it provides the highest client bitrate demands with less fluctuations compared to the other patterns, making it particularly suitable for our study. As our goal is to stress-test the system, replaying such part of the dataset is giving us the highest possible CU-UP utilization. Furthermore, the static pattern dataset has more entries compared to the mobility one, which improves its suitability to train the proposed ML model. Since our strategy in this paper is based on predicting the future estimated throughput (bitrate) values of the UEs, we performed feature selection, keeping only the DL bitrate feature and removing the remaining 25 columns available in the dataset, e.g. (Longitude, Latitude, PINGAVG, PINGMIN, PINGMAX and others), since they were either redundant or provided no significant contribution to the prediction task. As a training dataset for our LSTM model, we defined the concatenate of the three out of the five available day-snapshots, while the remaining two days were used to simulate the requirements of the two UEs. During the preprocessing stage, we performed min-max scaling within the operating values of our system (0-150 Mbps), and then performed smoothing through the spline interpolation technique in order to reduce the number of fluctuations, reducing the noise, making our data suitable for training a model.

B. Experiments

To evaluate the performance of our system, we conduct three types of experiments. Initially, we study a naive system that does not support the CU-UP scaling mechanism. A second experiment is conducted to measure the performance of a system that supports the CU-UP scaling mechanism, based on the real-time aggregating of throughput requirements of the UEs through the xApp in FlexRIC. We call this method as the reactive scaling method. At the same time, we evaluate the performance of a system that supports the CU-UP scaling mechanism in and out but based on the forecast future values of the requirements in the case of scale-out and scale-in. In the latter case, we forecast when the network shall scale-in, and

Fig. 3: Naive System: iPerf Bitrates vs Demands for UE1, UE2, and Aggregate.

Fig. 4: Reactive CU-UP Scaling: iPerf Bitrates vs Demands for UE1, UE2, and Aggregate.

Fig. 5: Proactive CU-UP Scaling: iPerf Bitrates vs Demands for UE1, UE2, and Aggregate.

when that timepoint is reached, we scale the network. This allows us to continuously serve clients up to the point that they stop demanding traffic, and then scale-in the network, based on the real-time metrics that we receive. We call this method the proactive scaling method. After conducting various experiments we found out that the version of the OAI-CU-UP we use can satisfy transmission requirements of clients up to 300 Mbps. The maximum traffic that a CU-UP can handle depends on the degree of CPU utilization based on incoming traffic since other resources (such as RAM usage) remained underutilized during the experiments. For the needs of this work, we limit the upper traffic boundary per CU-UP to 150 Mbps by assigning fewer resources to the scheduled pod. We argue that the usage of an upper limit for the maximum transmitted traffic of a CU-UP in our experiments does not violate the applicability of their results, since the performance characteristics of a CU-UP (v-RAN component) regarding maximum transmittable traffic are related to the assigned CPU resources [27]. Additionally, the upper and lower thresholds used in Algorithm 1 were set to 150 Mbps and 130 Mbps, respectively; these values can be adjusted based on the system configuration.

As mentioned in Section IV-A, two days of the dataset are

used to simulate client requirements. In the presented experiments, the client transmission requirements are simulated by injecting UDP traffic from the UPF to the UEs using the *iperf* application. Each value of the testing dataset corresponds to a UDP session of 1 second duration; for this reason, in Figures 4 and 5 no drop in the transmissions resulting from the scaling process, as described in Section III, is visible.

1) *Naive system*: In Figure 3, we show the performance of the naive 5G network to satisfy the requirements of the connected UEs under different load conditions. As we can see from Fig. 3a and 3b, the naive system is able to satisfy the needs of its connected UEs under normal conditions. However, the interesting part of the experiment is located between sessions 214 and 380 where the requirements of both UEs exceed 150 Mbps, which is the allowable traffic limit. Thus, the naive system is unable to satisfy the requirements of the UEs as it faces limitations in the available capacity of the CU-UP component. This snapshot simulates peak times, where the increased demand from multiple users causes congestion. This case highlights the importance of dynamically scaling network resources through mechanisms such as adaptive bandwidth allocation that implies the activation of additional CU-UP instances, which can respond in real-time to the change of

user demands.

2) *Reactive CU-UP scaling system*: In Figure 4, the graphs of the CU-UP Horizontal Scaling System based on real-time throughput monitoring under the same demand pattern are presented. As can be seen from Fig. 4a and 4b, this system is able to satisfy the demands of both of the connected UEs in the case of normal conditions. At the same time, by scaling the CU-UP instances it can satisfy the total demands of the clients even when they exceed the configured limits. This scaling mechanism is responsible for preventing the severe performance degradation observed in the naive system. Vertical green and blue lines mark the moments when scaling-out or in of the CU-UP instances was performed, respectively. Although this system successfully handles all the demands of the clients even under high peak loads, we observe that relying to the real-time monitoring, introduces packet loss for a short period of time until the scale-out process is completed. This is happening due to the readjustment of the number of CU-UP instances, as it happens after the detection of the overlimit traffic. Additionally, the system correctly scales in during the session no. 345 due to the decrease in demand for the next 10 sessions, but then the values of the client demands increase above the allowable limit from session 355 onwards, requiring the system to scale-out again. Given that short-term network adjustments entail considerable overhead, introducing a client demand forecasting mechanism could enhance the system's ability to anticipate changes, reducing unnecessary adjustments and ensuring smoother performance under fluctuating conditions.

3) *Proactive CU-UP scaling system*: In Figure 5, the graphs of a CU-UP Horizontal Scaling System using a prediction mechanism under the same demand pattern as the previous two experiments are presented. As shown in Fig. 5a and 5b, the system can satisfy the requirements of both UEs in normal and peak periods with high demand conditions. The LSTM described in subsection III-C is able to predict with satisfactory accuracy, and the forecast values are also shown in Fig. 5a and 5b. Through the forecasting mechanism, the proposed system performs proactive scaling at session 211, compared to the case of reactive scaling system, which performs scaling-out at session 218. Due to the proactive scaling, the 5G network is able to satisfy user demands throughout its operation, since this approach prevents the severe performance degradation and packet loss observed in the real-time monitoring system, as scaling operations are performed in advance of demand spikes. The green and blue lines mark the moments where scaling-out and in occur respectively.

Another advantage of the proactive scaling system over the reactive one is the prevention of the ping-pong scaling effect, characterized by unnecessary scale-in at session 345 followed by scale-out at session 355. By effectively predicting the future increase in UE requirements, the proposed system avoided these frequent adjustments of the CU-UP instances, which could otherwise introduce additional processing overhead and impact performance.

However, when the bandwidth values of the UEs are less than the threshold, the xApp triggers a scale-in system procedure, adhering to the desired operation. This behavior minimizes scaling overhead while ensuring sufficient capacity to accommodate fluctuating user demands. The forecasting mechanism thus enables efficient resource allocation and maintains high service quality, demonstrating its advantage over real-time monitoring alone.

V. DISCUSSION & LIMITATIONS

Our findings highlight the effectiveness of integrating a proactive CU-UP scaling mechanism in 5G O-RAN systems, as a means of mitigating network congestion and successfully maintaining optimal performance. The proposed method was validated in terms of its effectiveness compared to reactive methods. Using ML, more specifically an LSTM-based traffic prediction model, the proposed proactive CU-UP scaling mechanism effectively anticipates network load variations, ensuring timely scaling decisions that prevent congestion of the CU-UP component. Compared to existing works limited to simulation environments, our real-world deployment and evaluation emphasize the applicability and feasibility of such mechanism integration in 5G commercial networks.

Given the time-sensitive nature of our proposed system, since decision-making happens on a real-time controller, greater emphasis could be placed on minimizing the ML inference time by exploring alternative models that could lead to measurable improvements in the system performance. Since our prediction implementation relies on a pre-trained model, the SMO could frequently retrain the model with new incoming data traffic to enhance adaptability and improve the system's accuracy.

Our proposed mechanism can also be extended to address similar network congestion bottlenecks, such as the UPF in the 5GCN or DUs in scenarios involving multiple RUs. However, an important aspect not discussed in this paper is the placement of scaled CU-UP instances to minimize overall latency in a 5G network. The placement problem could be formulated as an optimization problem to determine the optimal placement strategy for the scaled CU-UP instances across the available nodes, aiming to maximize data traffic while minimizing latency constraints.

The proposed scheme has the potential to address other aspects impacting the network as well. For example, monitoring the load that each RAN component gets can be directly projected to the carbon footprint of the respective component. This in turn can be adjusted to a proactive scaling-in order to maintain the overall energy efficiency of the infrastructure. Similarly, proactive scaling can be applied as a method to mitigate vulnerabilities as they are detected in the network. For example, in case of identifying that the system is being used by malicious users, the users/slice that they belong can be transferred to a constrained CU-UP instance, so as to limit their overall impact to the system.

Nevertheless, the greatest limitation of our approach is the absence of the CU-UP Change procedure in our setup. This

absence has been managed in our experimental procedure, in order to impact our results in the least possible manner, by redirecting the traffic of already connected UEs through instances of the CU-UP that already exist. This has been validated through our experimental results and was proven to have no impact on the scaling decision and the overall throughput that we manage to get, but merely impacts the seamless experience that a real user shall get over the system.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have implemented a real-world 5G O-RAN network with a proactive CU-UP scaling mechanism designed to forecast traffic demands using a LSTM model. Our system utilizes real-world testbed environment in order to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed system under dynamic network conditions. Based on the outcomes of our experiments, we validated that a proactive CU-UP scaling mechanism can enhance the ability of the system to maintain the QoS by performing a CU-UP scaling before the peak periods occur. We also highlight the importance of integrating ML models to forecast the network load since this integration minimizes packet loss, reduces unnecessary scaling overhead, and ensures a smoother operation during high-demand periods. For future work, we aim to expand our approach by incorporating additional RAN components into the scaling mechanism and investigating optimization strategies for CU-UP placement, in order to minimize the latency and maximize the throughput performance among the UE and the 5G network. As the system utilization can directly impact the overall footprint of the infrastructure, scaling of network functions can significantly impact the overall energy consumption of the network. Therefore, we seek to further explore energy-efficient scaling strategies that can balance the system performance with power consumption, which is becoming a key factor in making 5G networks more sustainable.

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